

Evaluation of District wise Differences in Proper Implementation of Different Activities in the Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (KGBV)

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Abstract

Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya are residential school which covers hard to reach girls especially the deprived ones belonging predominantly to the SC, ST, OBC community and minority groups. It also seeks to evaluate the operational and management issues in the running of KGBVs and hostels, such as the quality of teachers, safety and security of girls, infrastructural provision, financial norms of the scheme, etc. Multistage sampling technique was adopted for conducting the study. The state of Assam in India was selected for conducting the study. The six districts namely Dibrugarh, Sibsagar, Lakhimpur, Nagaon, Kamrup and Barpeta were selected purposively for the study. Observation method was mainly used for the study; it involves the direct observation of phenomenon in their natural settings. Although there was differences in conducting the activities in different districts, but no major differences were observed. It may be because the same guideline and instructions were provided by the Mission Director and State Programme Officer, Sarba Siksha Abhijan, Assam to the entire District at the same time. Generally the differences were observed when the district official, block official or the KGBV functionaries do not act and follow the orders accordingly or show negligence and give less importance to the work.

Keywords: Evaluation, differences, implementation, activities, Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya

1. Introduction

Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya are residential school which covers hard to reach girls especially the deprived ones belonging predominantly to the SC, ST, OBC community and minority groups. This is an intervention for girls residing in small and scattered habitations far off from the nearest school. Under this scheme, residential schools and hostel facilities for girls is established in the Educationally Backward Blocks (EBBs), towns and minority concentrated areas, all over the country. The criteria followed for setting up the schools are - blocks with rural female literacy below the national average and gender gap in literacy more than the national average and minority population above 20% (as per Census 2001). The main objectives of the Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya scheme are: Facilitate retention of girls, ensure greater participation of girls in education, develop and promote facilities to provide access to girls belonging to disadvantaged groups like SC and ST, improve quality of education and stress upon the relevance and quality of girls' education for their empowerment. When these schools are more established and well accepted as a significant component of SSA. The main purpose of the study is to assess whether the objectives of the KGBV scheme are being met and whether this intervention has facilitated greater participation of girls at the upper primary stage of education in term of their enrolment, attendance and learning achievements. It also seeks to evaluate the operational and management issues in the running of KGBVs and hostels, such as the quality of teachers, safety and security of girls, infrastructural provision, financial norms of the scheme, etc

2. Objectives of the Study

To evaluate the District wise differences in proper implementation of different activities in KGBVs

3. Research Methodology

Multistage sampling technique was adopted for conducting the study. The state of Assam in India was selected for conducting the study. The six districts namely Dibrugarh, Sibsagar, Lakhimpur, Nagaon, Kamrup and Barpeta were selected purposively for the study. Out of the selected districts:

- In Dibrugarh there is 1 KGBV covering 50 children and it falls under Model 2
- In Sibsagar there is 1 KGBV covering 50 children and it falls under Model 2
- In Lakhimpur there is 1 KGBV covering 50 children and it falls under Model 2
- In Nagoan there is 1 KGBV covering 50 children and it falls under Model 2
- In Kamrup there are 2 KGBVs covering 200 children and it falls under Model 1
- In Barpeta there are 3 KGBVs covering 200 children and 1 KGBV falls under Model 1 and 2 KGBVs falls under Model 2

A total number of nine KGBVs were selected for the study. The KGBVs of the different District were established under different blocks.

DISTRICT	→	BLOCK
1. Dibrugarh	→	Panitola
2. Sibsagar	→	Pachim Abhayapur
3. Lakhimpur	→	North Lakhimpur
4. Nagoan	→	Batadrava
5. Kamrup	→	Goroimari
6. Barpeta	→	Chamaria
	→	Mondia
	→	Barpeta Gobardhana

Observation method was mainly used because it provides the researcher with ways to check for nonverbal expression of feelings, determine who interacts with whom, grasp how participant communicate with each other, and check for how much time is spent on various activities (Schmuck, 1997). Participant observation method helped the researchers to observe events that informants were unable or unwilling to share. Selective observation was used in which the researcher focuses on different type of activities to help delineate the differences in those activities (Angrosino *et al.*, 2000). The observation method was mainly used in the study to see the district wise differences in proper implementation of the different activities in the KGBV. It involves the direct observation of phenomenon in their natural settings. Here the researcher interacted and observed the situation so as to get a clear picture of the programme.

4. Research Findings

The district wise difference was observed based on the following criteria: infrastructure facilities, management system, co-curricular and curriculum activities, performance of children and health care facilities provided in KGBV.

Panitola KGBV (Dibrugarh district) - 50 girls

- The KGBV of Panitola was established in own Assam type building in the year 2007 with a good boundary wall facility and a big play ground. The quality of construction work was good.
- The KGBV was properly maintained with a beautiful flower garden and kitchen garden all around which adds to the aesthetic value of the KGBV.
- There was sufficient room to accommodate the girls of KGBV and also adequate facilities for seating arrangement in the classroom.
- The toilets and bathrooms were cleaned every day, and maintained hygienically.
- The over all monitoring of the KGBV was done by DPO (AS).
- Five numbers of teachers were present in the KGBV and two numbers of posts were lying vacant.
- The fund for running the KGBV was received timely.
- The classes were functioned regularly for more than five hours, from 8.15 am – 2.30 pm.
- The evaluations were conducted weekly, monthly and quarterly and the remedial teaching was organized for the slow learners regularly by full time teachers.
- Here the vocational training was given much importance and different items were prepared by the girls. Weaving of mekhala-chadar and gamucha by the girls was the special attraction in the KGBV. Different trades were generally taught by short-term contractual teacher appointed for the purpose. This creates an opportunity for the girls to generate their own income in future
- The grades received by the girls of KGBV were A grade-3, B grade-20, C grade-19, D grade-7.
- Parents-teachers meeting were organized in the KGBV to discuss various issues related to over all development.
- Health camps were not organized in the KGBV. No proper health record in the form of register was maintained to keep the detail records of the health of girls.

- Knowledge on reproductive health was not provided to the adolescent girls by the warden, teachers and matron of the KGBV.

Pachim Abhyapur KGBV (Sibsagar district) - 50 girls

- The KGBV of Pachim Abhyapur was established in own Assam type building in the year 2010 with a good boundary wall facility and a big play ground. The quality of construction work was good.
- Although there was no flower garden, yet the KGBV had few plants and flowers pots.
- The living rooms of the girls were very well maintained and all the belongings of the girls were very nicely kept. The rooms were sufficient to accommodate the girls of KGBV and all the classrooms had adequate facilities such as blackboard, sitting arrangement, etc.
- Though the KGBV had the provision of running water in the toilets and bathrooms, but these were not maintained by the girls up to the satisfactory level.
- The over all monitoring of the KGBV was done by DPO (AS).
- Five numbers of teachers were present in the KGBV and two numbers of posts were lying vacant.
- Although fund for running the KGBV was received timely, but the caretaker of the KGBV had expressed dissatisfaction towards the block level functionaries and district level functionaries for not sending the guideline for expenditure to be done in the KGBV.
- The classes functioned regularly for more than five hours, from 8.45 am -1.35 pm.
- The evaluations were basically conducted quarterly and remedial teaching was organized by the teachers by conducting extra classes for slow learners by the full time teachers.
- In Pachim Abhyapur KGBV, the vocational training was given much importance and girls were found to learn many skills such as embroidery, fabric painting, jute work and soft toys preparation. The girls were also found to be very much involved in preparation of wall magazine and it was displayed very nicely.
- The grades received by the girls of the KGBV were A grade-3, B grade-13, C grade-34 and D grade-0.

- Parents-teachers meeting were regularly conducted in the KGBV to discuss various issues related to health, academic achievement of the girls etc.
- Health camps were not organized in the KGBV. Although the health record register was available in the KGBV, but it was not updated regularly.
- Knowledge on reproductive health was provided to the girls of the KGBV by the teacher during the class hours.
- The girls of the KGBV were also found to be very active in many cultural activities such as singing, dancing, etc.

North Lakhimpur KGBV (Lakhimpur district) - 50 girls

- The KGBV of North Lakhimpur was established in own RCC building in the year 2008 surrounded by a proper boundary wall and a big play ground.
- Although adequate space was seen in the KGBV, but there was no flower garden and kitchen garden in the KGBV.
- Although the quality of construction was good but the surrounding and environment was not properly maintained and cleaned.
- There was sufficient room to accommodate the girls of KGBV and also adequate facilities for seating arrangement in the classrooms. The girls' rooms were clean but the light in the rooms was not found sufficient. It would definitely affect the eyesight of the girls in future.
- The toilets and bathrooms were clean and hygienic with adequate water facilities.
- The overall monitoring of the KGBV was done by DPO (AS).
- Six numbers of teachers were present in the KGBV and one post was lying vacant.
- The fund for running the KGBV was received timely but the expenditure was basically done at district and block level as the post of caretaker was vacant.
- The classes were functioning regularly for five hours, from 8.45 am-1.35 pm.
- The evaluation was conducted weekly and quarterly and the remedial teaching was organized for slow learners by holding extra classes by the teachers.

- Although vocational training was organized for the girls, it was observed that they were not experts in the skills as the items prepared were not up to the mark. Special care should be taken in selecting trades and only an instructor who can give his/her best should be appointed. The girls of KGBV were expert in conducting assembly.
- The performance of the girls in North Lakhimpur KGBV was almost satisfactory as the grades received by the girls were A grade-27, B grade-12, C grade-10 and D grade-0.
- Parents-teachers meetings was regularly organized in the KGBV and various issues such as cleanliness and maintenance of hygiene and academic support at home, etc. were discussed.
- Health camps were once organized to assess the health status of the girls at KGBV. No proper health record in the form of register was maintained in the KGBV.
- Knowledge on reproductive health was not provided to the adolescent girls by any of the KGBV functionaries.
- The fund for running the KGBV was received timely.
- The classes functioned regularly for five hours, from 9.30 am-2.15 pm.
- The evaluation was held daily, quarterly and remedial teaching was organized for the slow learners by peers who are experts and special care was taken by the teachers.
- Although vocational training was conducted for the girls but the trade selected was not found to benefit them. So proper selection of experts and trade is very much essential. Girls of Batardrava KGBV were found to be expert in self defense skills.
- The grades received by the girls of the KGBV were A grade-5, B grade-17, C grade-11, D grade-5.
- Parents-teacher meeting was regularly organized in the KGBV to discuss various issues related to girls' absenteeism, academic achievement, etc.
- Health camp was not organized in the KGBV. Health record registers were also not maintained by the KGBV functionaries.
- Knowledge on reproductive health was provided to the girls in the KGBV by the teachers.

Batadrava KGBV (Nagaon district) - 50 girls

- The KGBV of Batadrava was established in a rented Assam type building in the year 2011. The building has proper boundary wall and a big play ground.
- In spite of sufficient space there was no flower garden and vegetable garden in the KGBV, to enhance its aesthetic appeal.
- The hostel accommodation was pucca and the classrooms were constructed with temporary bamboo walls.
- Desks and benches were provided in the KGBV classroom, but there was a lot of scope for improvement in classroom environment, by incorporating some more teaching-learning materials in the KGBV.
- Toilets and bathrooms were not sufficient in the KGBV. There was no provision of running water in the KGBV. In most of the cases, the girls had to use hand pumps.
- The overall monitoring was done by DPO (AS). The KGBV was also visited by present Education Minister and former Education Minister of Assam.
- Six numbers of teachers were presented in the KGBV and there was no vacancy in the KGBV.

Goroimari KGBV (Kamrup district) – 100 girls

- The KGBV of Goroimari was established in own RCC type building in the year 2008 with a proper boundary wall and a play ground. The area was very prone to water blockage due to improper drainage facility. The construction of the building was found good.
- There was no flower garden and kitchen garden seen in the KGBV and the reason was mainly due to water blockage.
- There was sufficient room to accommodate the girls of KGBV and adequate facilities for seating arrangement in the classrooms.
- The toilets and bathrooms were clean. Although there was provision for running water, but the water tank was placed at the same level with the bathrooms and toilets, so the water does not flow sufficiently. The girls had to use hand pump most of the times.
- The environment of the KGBV was not clean and hygiene was not maintained. The kitchen was kutcha and it was not kept clean. The classrooms were not maintained properly and

the things were found to be scattered and not cleaned regularly.

- The overall monitoring was done by DPO (AS).
- Only two numbers of teachers were present in the KGBV and five numbers of posts were lying vacant. The warden was seemed to be a young inexperienced girl who lacks the managerial skills. Therefore training was required for proper management.
- The fund for running the KGBV was received timely.
- The classes were functioning but it was not regular. The timing is for three hours only from 9 am to 12 pm, due to lack of teachers in the KGBV.
- The evaluation was conducted quarterly and remedial teaching was conducted in group, for slow learners by the peers group.
- In Goroimari KGBV, the vocational training was organized by contractual teachers. Teachers who knew different trades in KGBV were also involved.
- The grades received by the girls of KGBV were A grade-4, B grade-18, C grade-45, D grade-28.
- Parents-teachers meeting were organized in the KGBV to discuss issues on discipline and academic support. Parent showed their concern about non-availability of teachers in the KGBV.
- Health camp was organized once before the visit of Joint Review Mission (JRM) and health records were available in KGBV. But the registers were not updated regularly due to lack of teaching staff and more work load due to large numbers of girls.
- Knowledge on reproductive health was imparted to the girls by Asha Karmi and sometimes by the teachers.

Chamaria KGBV (Kamrup District) – 100 girls

- The KGBV of Chamaria was established in the block mission office of Assam in an Assam type building in the year 2008 with a very dilapidated condition without any play ground. The warden informed that very soon they were going to shift to a new building which was under construction.
- There was no adequate space for play ground and garden in the KGBV.

- The rooms were not sufficient to accommodate the girls of KGBV and the classroom environment was not favorable.
- The toilets and bathrooms were in bad condition with blockage problem. Twenty numbers of girls were send to their home as there was no adequate number of toilet facilities in the KGBV on the day of data collection.
- The overall monitoring of the KGBV was done by DPO (AS).
- Five numbers of teachers were present in the KGBV and two numbers of posts were lying vacant.
- The fund for running the KGBV was received timely.
- The classes were functioned regularly for five hours, from 10 am - 3 pm.
- The evaluations were conducted weekly and quarterly. As informed by the warden the remedial teaching was not conducted in the KGBV.
- Although vocational training was conducted but the trades were not selected with proper care. Accordingly the girls were not benefited much and no end products could be seen in the KGBV. The girls were good in cultural activities such as dancing, singing and role play.
- The grades received by the girls of KGBV were A grade-0, B grade-12 and C grade-13. The records of girls were not kept properly and could not be produced during data collection.
- Parents-teachers meetings were organized in the KGBV to discuss issues on daily living skills, academic achievement, etc.
- Although the block PHC was just opposite to the KGBV but it was observed that no health camp were organized for assessing the health status of the girls in the KGBV. Health records are also not maintained to keep the detail records of the health of the girls.
- Knowledge on reproductive health was provided to the adolescent girls by the teachers in the KGBV.

Barpeta town KGBV (Barpeta district) – 50 girls

- The KGBV of Barpeta town was established in a rented Assam type building in the year 2011

and the surrounding was bounded by tins and it had a small area for play ground.

- Since the KGBV was in rented building, there was no space for kitchen garden and flower garden.
- The living rooms of the girls were small and congested and there was not much space for the girls to accommodate their belongings. The rooms for girls were concrete but the classrooms were constructed with bamboo wall and tins. The furniture and other things in the classroom were not so satisfactory and there was no proper facility for electricity in the classrooms.
- Toilets and bathrooms were clean but there was no running water facility. The girls had to fetch water from the hand pump. With proper support it can be kept cleaner.
- The overall monitoring was done by DPO (AS).
- Three numbers of teachers were present and two posts were lying vacant.
- The fund for running the KGBV was not received timely from the district and block level, as a result of which they had to face many problems in management of KGBV.
- The classes were regularly functioning in the KGBV for five hours, from 10 am - 3 pm.
- The evaluations were mainly conducted weekly and quarterly and the remedial teaching was generally organized for the girls after the term end evaluation which was not found to be much effective for the girls.
- Although vocational training was organized for the girls more inputs should be given, and the trades should be selected properly so that it helps the learners to generate their own income in future. Workshop was organized for ten days to teach them singing and dancing. Girls were not found to be involved in self defense activities much.
- The grades received by the girls of KGBV were A grade-0, B grade-5, C grade-20, D grade-23.
- Parents-teachers meetings were organized in the KGBV to discuss various issues related to girls' well-being, such as academic achievement, daily living skills, prevention of child marriage, etc.

- Health camps were not organized for the girls and no proper health records were available in the KGBV.
- Knowledge on reproductive health was provided to the girls by the matron, teachers and also discussed among peers.

Gobardhana KGBV (Barpeta district) - 50 girls

- The KGBV of Gobardhana of Barpeta district was established in a rented RCC building in the year 2011. It has a big play ground and there was no boundary wall in the KGBV.
- Although adequate space was seen in the KGBV but there was no flower garden and kitchen garden in the KGBV. It was in the residential area and in the opposite of the KGBV there was a namghar.
- The top floors were used for accommodation of the girls, warden and other staffs. The ground floor was used as classrooms and kitchen. The living rooms of the girls were congested to accommodate all the girls of KGBV. The classrooms have adequate facilities such as desks, benches, black boards, etc.
- The toilets and bathrooms were not maintained properly, since there was no provision of running water. The girls had to collect water from hand pump and carry to the top floor for bath and toilet purpose.
- The overall monitoring of the KGBV was done by DPO (AS).
- Four numbers of teachers were present in the KGBV and two numbers of posts were lying vacant.
- The fund for running the KGBV was not received timely from the block and district level. Accordingly the KGBV functionaries have to face lots of problem in smooth functioning of KGBV.
- The classes were regularly conducted by the teacher for more than five hours, from 9.30 am - 3.00 pm.
- The evaluations were conducted daily and quarterly and remedial teaching was also organized for the girls by group learning.
- Vocational training was organized for the girls; they have made many embroidery and fabric paint work which were really very beautiful. This will help the girls to generate income later. Workshops were also organized for the girls for music and dance and they have

adopted the skills very nicely. The girls were also good in self defense skills.

- The grades received by the girls of the KGBV were A grade-6, B grade-22, C grade-21, D grade-1.
- Parents-teacher meetings were organized in the KGBV to discuss various issues related to academic achievement, health issues, etc.
- Health camps were not organized in the KGBV. But health records were maintained in the KGBV.
- Knowledge on reproductive health was explained to the adolescent girls by the teacher of the KGBV.

Mondia KGBV (Barpeta District) -100 girls

- The KGBV of Mondia was established in a rented Assam type building in the year 2008 and the entire surrounding was bounded by tin sheets. It was located in char area and is dominated by minority community people. A small area inside the KGBV was utilized by the girls as play ground.
- There was no space in the KGBV for flower garden and kitchen garden.
- The living rooms of the girls were small and it was very congested to accommodate hundred numbers of girls. The rooms were dark and there was no proper place to store their belongings. The construction of the KGBV was done by bamboo walls and tin sheets.
- Although the class rooms were of tin sheets and bamboo walls, but it was arranged very nicely with all adequate facilities including electricity supply.
- The toilets and bathrooms could not be maintained properly due to large numbers of girls'. The girls were also seen to take bath in open place with a temporary shed.
- The overall monitoring of the KGBV was done by DPO (AS).
- Six numbers of teachers were present in the KGBV and one number of post was lying vacant.
- The fund for the KGBV was not received timely from the district and block level. This created problem in proper functioning of the KGBV.
- The classes were functioned regularly for more than five hours from 9.30 am - 3.00 pm.

- The evaluations of the girls were held monthly and quarterly. The remedial teaching was also held for the girls during holidays at evening hours.
- Vocational trainings were organized for the girls in different trades such as knitting, embroidery, cutting and tailoring. The girls have learned the skill and it will definitely help them in future. The girls were also seen to learn different self defense skills in the KGBV.
- The grades received by the girls of KGBV were A grade-8, B grade-29, C grade-11 and D grade-22.
- Parents-teachers meetings were organized in the KGBV to discuss various issues related to academic achievement, health, etc.
- Health camps were not organized in the KGBV. But registers to record the health status of the girls were maintained and updated regularly.
- Knowledge on reproductive health was provided to the girls in the KGBV and it was basically provided by the teachers of the KGBV.

5. Conclusion

From the above findings it can be concluded that although there was differences in conducting the activities in different districts, but no major differences were observed. It may be because the same guideline and instructions were provided by the Mission Director and State Programme Officer, Sarba Siksha Abhijan, Assam to the entire District at the same time. Accordingly they were supposed to abide by the order and do the needful.

Generally the differences were observed when the district official, block official or the KGBV functionaries do not act and follow the orders accordingly or show negligence and give less importance to the work. But to make the KGBV programme successful, the functionaries of KGBV at all the levels have to work in cooperation and with mission mode.

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